

Work Motivation in Improving the Performance of Bank Sulsebar Employees at the Majene Branch Office, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: *This study aims to explain work motivation in improving employee performance at Bank Sulsebar Majene Branch Office. The method used is qualitative with phenomenological research type. The results showed that (1) a form of work motivation that was able to improve the performance of the employees of the Bank Sulsebar Majene Branch Office in addition to the basic salary, also received a bonus 4 times a year, intended for employees as a reward for doing a good job; (2) With good work motivation, employees at Bank Sulsebar Majene Branch can improve their performance. Employees have a very high responsibility and morale.*

KEYWORDS: *Work motivation, employee performance*

I. INTRODUCTION

The main basis of banking activities is trust, both in raising funds and in distributing funds.

But along with its development, many problems related to banking. The main problem is the regulation of the financial system which is closely related to the mechanism for determining the amount of money circulating in the economy. The financial system which consists of the financial authority, banking system and non-bank financial institution system is basically an order in the economy of a country that plays a major role in providing financial service facilities.

In general, banking institutions can be grouped into two forms, namely bank financial institutions and non-bank financial institutions. The banking system in Indonesia is distinguished by its function, which consists of the Central Bank, Commercial Banks, and Rural Banks. Commercial Banks can collect funds from the public directly in the form of demand deposits, savings and deposits, then distribute them to the public, especially in the form of credit or other forms. Commercial banks in their activities provide services in payment traffic, while rural banks are based on laws and regulations in collecting funds, but are not allowed to accept demand deposits and are not allowed to provide services in payment traffic. While the types of non-bank financial institutions can be in the form of financing institutions, venture model companies, factoring companies, consumer finance companies, credit card companies, pension funds, pawnshops, capital markets and others.

This service facility is provided by financial institutions, including private banks as government partners. Therefore, employee performance and motivation of bank employees must be owned by every banking employee, especially at the branch office of Bank Sulsebar Majene. One of the factors that increase employee performance is motivation and job satisfaction. So that every employee must have the strength and drive to change within himself, this driving force is called motivation.

There are two factors that influence motivation, namely: a) intrinsic factors, namely factors that arise from within the individual. As an indicator of these factors is the desire to achieve and develop the quality of personal life. 2) Extrinsic factors, namely factors that come from outside the individual that will affect him in his work. Extrinsic factors consist of: the type of work itself, job status, workplace, job security, decent income, recognition and rewards, trust in doing work, good leadership, fairness and administrative discretion. With high motivation, it is expected that employee performance will increase, so that organizational goals can be achieved quantitatively and qualitatively, employees have creativity, flexibility and reliability, and other achievements desired by the organization.

While performance management is a process designed to link organizational goals with individual goals, so that the two goals meet. The role of humans is what can make humans as resources who play an important role in a company. Because of this role, people can be said to be one of the most important assets owned by a company. An asset of course must be properly maintained, therefore human resources become one part of the company that must receive considerable attention. If human resources can be developed properly, then these human resources can assist the company in achieving its goals in accordance with the desired target.

Motivation also has an influence on employee performance and is one of the important factors experienced by companies, especially regarding what can motivate employees and how to convey it to employees. Because employees also want to be noticed and appreciated at work, any form of company concern for their employees will make them feel that they are an important part of an organization (company), thus motivating them.

To improve the quality of employees, Bank Sulselbar feels the need to improve several things, including work motivation and employee job satisfaction. In this case, the employees of Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch have their own way of motivating employees.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted by taking the location of the Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch Office, West Sulawesi Province. The type of research used is qualitative with the type of case study research. This type of qualitative research is intended to describe descriptively the object of research or what is the point of interest based on facts (Sugiyono, 2012). The object under study is work motivation in improving employee performance at Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) Forms of Work Motivation in Improving Employee Performance at Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch

In Herzberg's theory of motivation, the driving factors include: achievement, recognition, responsibility, progress, the work itself and the possibility of developing: a). Achievement is the need to obtain achievement in the field of work handled. A person who has a desire for achievement as a "need" can encourage him to achieve goals; b). Recognition is the need to obtain recognition from the leadership for the work/work that has been achieved; c). Responsibility is the need to acquire responsibility in the area of work being handled; d). Progress is the need to obtain career advancement (position); e). The work itself (the work it self) is the need to be able to handle work actively according to their interests and talents; f). The possibility of growth is a necessity for career advancement. Frederick Herzberg divided Maslow's hierarchy of needs into lower-level needs (physiological, security, and social) and higher-order needs (esteem and self-actualization).

Based on the results of the researcher's observations, the form of motivation that can improve employee performance at the Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch Office is income consisting of salary, allowances, leave money, THR, year-end bonuses, production services, clothing and food. In addition, Bank Sulsel also provides additional bonuses 3 times a year, if the profit earned increases.

If we look at the hierarchy of needs according to Maslow, then the motivation of the employees of Bank Sulselbar is already at a high level of needs (esteem and self-actualization). Herzberg argues that the best way to motivate someone is to fulfill their higher needs (Hasibuan, 2003).

As the results of research by Triyanto and Sudarwati (2014), show that giving awards has a positive and significant effect on employee work motivation. The forms of awards that can be given include decent salaries, bonuses and promotions. The results of Kusuma's research (2017), show that there is a significant effect of salary on employee work motivation.

From the results of this study, it shows that the form of motivation given to employees of Bank Sulselbar Majene branch office is in accordance with the conditions desired by employees.

2) Employee Performance Improvement of Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch Office

Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch is a fairly large company and has quite a number of employees, namely as many as 50 employees, so in carrying out its activities the company is very dependent on the performance of employees so that the company continues to progress and develop. This study aims to determine the efforts to improve employee performance through the motivation given. Employee productivity becomes the center of attention in an effort to improve performance that affects the level of efficiency and effectiveness of the organization.

Employee performance can be influenced by ability and motivation factors, where if the employee's ability and motivation given by the company are good, then employee performance will be maximized and employee productivity will increase. In this study, the results of observations and interviews with informants showed that efforts to improve the performance of employees of the Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch office were as expected. According to the results of the interview, it shows that the increase in employee performance is largely determined by the employee's work motivation. Even from the number of informants interviewed, 60% of them stated that their performance increased because it was driven by their own motivation to work better and was supported by motivation that came from the management, namely in the form of compensation which was considered to be in accordance with their expectations.

The results of research by Nurcahyani and Adnyani (2016), show that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee job satisfaction. That is, the higher the employee's motivation towards the company, the higher the employee's performance will be. From the results of the study, Firmandari (2014) shows that salaries and benefits moderated by motivation have a significant positive effect on the performance of bank employees. From this research, it shows that the form of motivation in the form of salary and allowances is very influential on the satisfaction and performance of bank employees.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The form of motivation that can increase the work motivation of employees of the Bank Sulselbar Majene Branch Office, one of which is compensation in the form of salaries, allowances, bonuses and promotions. The better the reward system, the more motivated employees will be to work and bring out all their potential. This increase in motivation is very influential and significant to increase employee performance.

With the increase in the performance of these employees, it will of course also improve the quality of Bank Sulselbar's services to its customers. From this research, it is important for the leadership of the South Sulawesi bank to map out an ideal and fair compensation system for its employees. Giving motivation to employees is important to always do so that it can generate encouragement in employees to continue to innovate to provide the best service to customers.

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